

CLASSIFICATION AND PROPERTIES OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL TEXTILE PREFORMS

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Three representative geometric units

Abstract: The three-dimensional (3D) textile preforms were used as the reinforcing phase of the textile structural composites, and its geometry effected the physical and mechanical properties of the composites. In this paper, the 3D textile preforms were classified, and three representative geometric units (RGUs) were proposed, namely orthogonal geometric unit, skew geometric unit and curved geometric unit. Other units were combinations and derivations of these three RGUs. The relationship and performance characterization of three RGUs were discussed. The concepts of rigid structure, flexible structure and elastoplastic structure were proposed. The fiber volume fraction, strength and strain characteristics of different structural preforms were predicted. The classification of 3D textile preforms was conducive to the relationship between geometries and performances, forming a technical system, and providing a theoretical basis for the selection of composites with different properties.

Three representative geometric units

3D textile preforms were a kind of fiber bundle collections with periodicity and anisotropy. The representative volume element was usually used to discuss the meso-geometric structure of the preforms. In view of the numbers, distribution, interweave mode and the complexity of fibers in 3D textile preforms, the RGUs have been divided into three types namely, orthogonal geometric unit, curved geometric unit and skew geometric unit.

As shown in the Fig. 1, the yarns in orthogonal units were along the Cartesian coordinate. In the internal RGUs of the 3D textile preforms, the directions of the yarns were mainly distributed in the three axes directions. The curved geometric unit contained the buckling yarns in the minimum representative volume element. Due to the buckling yarns, the proportion of unit fibers could be adjusted adaptively to suit the unit size. The yarns in skew geometric unit were assumed that the distributions were in a straight line and form a certain angle in space. A kind of skew geometric unit was shown in Fig. 1(c), and the number of yarn segments was uncertain. The representation of single yarn segment in space coordinate was illustrated, and the geometrical parameters of the yarns were explained.

Fig. 1 Three representative geometric units.

The relationship of the three RGUs

The meso-structure and transformation of the fibers affect the performance of the preforms, which in turn affect the properties of 3D textile composites. The properties of fibers in preforms were mainly characterized by the directions and curvatures of the textile yarns. As shown in Fig. 2, two coordinate axes expressed the two properties of the fibers in preforms.

In addition to these three representative geometric units, the other unit types were also existed in 3D textile preforms. The other unit types could be regarded as the combination and derived of these three units. The other units were composed of two or three afore-mentioned units. As shown in Fig. 3, the final unit was obtained by the two types of the three representative geometric units.

Fig. 2 The connection of three RGUs.

Fig. 3 The genomic assemblies of these RGUs.

3D textile preforms

The definition of rigid structure, flexible structure and elastoplastic structure have been proposed. These three structural preforms corresponding to the three RGUs were classified. 3D orthogonal preform, angle-interlock preform and four-step braided preform were introduced to further explain the classification of 3D textile preforms, as shown in Fig. 4. These representative structures were composed of the relevant geometric units, and the structure possessed the characteristic mechanical properties.

The preforms of rigid structure were mainly formed by the orthogonal geometric units. The symmetry structure and straight fibers of the preforms made the excellent properties of the composites. The flexible structural preforms were constituted by major curved geometric units. The preforms with elastoplastic structure were composed of skew geometric units. The multi-directional skew structure possessed elastic-plastic property, the number of increasing and decreasing units of the special-shaped yarn bundle was discontinuous, and the corresponding point was abrupt elastic-plastic property.

Fig. 4 The relevance of three RGUs and preforms.

The relationship of three representative structures

The mechanical property of 3D textile composites was mainly decided by the geometric structure of the preforms. There was a certain relationship among these geometric structures, as shown in Fig 5. The preform in the initial statement was the flexible structure, and the curved yarns in the unit had the larger curvature. With the increase of force, the buckling yarns gradually straightened up to the straight yarns in the elastoplastic structures. Finally, the preform was turned to the rigid structure.

Fig. 5 The relationship of three representative structures.